

PREDICTING AND MONITORING EL NINO

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Abstract

The El Niño/Southern Oscillation (ENSO) phenomenon is the most prominent global climate signal on the seasonal-interannual time scale. It is associated with major fluctuations in the tropical Pacific Ocean and atmosphere, anomalies in monsoon rainfall, and wintertime climate anomalies in the higher latitudes of both hemispheres. It also results in major disruption of the marine ecosystem along the west coast of the Americas.

The general nature of an ENSO episode is described. The 1982/83 ENSO was among the most intense of the past 100 years and differed in important respects from the typical pattern of events. Research and operational oceanic data acquired during this episode was far superior to that obtained during previous El Niño's, and allowed limited real time monitoring of the anomalies.

A ten year international research program to study the role of the tropical oceans in interannual climate variability begins in 1985. Plans for the ocean monitoring and prediction element of this program are reviewed.

1. Introduction

Once thought of as only an isolated local phenomenon, the El Niño event of the eastern tropical Pacific is in reality a key part of the complex system of climate fluctuations now generally referred to as the El Niño/Southern Oscillation (ENSO) phenomenon. The Southern Oscillation (SO) (Walker, 1924), is the dominant global climate signal on time scales of a few months to a few years. Its relative contribution to climate variability is largest in the tropical Pacific, where at irregular intervals of 2-10 years it enters an extreme, "low index" phase, characterized by abnormally high pressure over the Australian-Indonesian region and abnormally low pressure over the southeast Pacific. It is associated with major dislocations of the circulation and rainfall regimes in the tropics which bring drought to productive agricultural areas and torrential rains to otherwise arid regions. ENSO circulation anomalies also extend deep into the extratropics, bringing unusual wintertime conditions to mid-latitude locations

as far apart as the United States and New Zealand.

2. ENSO Episodes

2.1 Antecedent Conditions

The length, evolution, and timing relative to the seasonal cycle are strikingly similar for most ENSO events. Composite analyses of the evolution of the tropical Pacific sea surface temperature (SST) anomalies during six warm episodes between 1950 and 1976 were described by Rasmusson and Carpenter (1982) (Figure 1). The year preceding the event [year(-1)] is often (e.g. 1964, 1971, 1975), but not always (e.g. 1962, 1968, 1981) characterized by a stronger than normal Indonesian-Australian surface pressure trough and Southeast Pacific High, i.e. high SO index (SOI) conditions as characteristically defined by the Tahiti minus Darwin surface pressure difference. The east-west pressure gradient, and associated surface easterlies along the equator are stronger than normal; SST's are below normal in the central and eastern equatorial Pacific, and the associated equatorial dry zone is strongly developed so that rainfall near the dateline is near or below normal.

The first subtle changes in the high index regime typically appear during the last few months of year(-1) (Figure 1A). The SOI begins to fall, primarily because of decreasing positive pressure anomalies in the central and southeast Pacific reflected at Tahiti. The surface pressure gradient along the equator slackens as do the relatively strong easterlies west of the dateline. Positive SST anomalies often appear near the dateline, as rainfall anomalies between 160°E-180° show a trend toward positive values. In the admittedly data-poor region west of Chile, there is also a suggestion of positive SST anomalies perhaps associated with the weakening Southeast Pacific High.

2.2 Development of El Niño

The rapid anomalous El Niño warming near the Peru coast usually begins late in year(-1) or early in the following year(0), roughly in phase with the normal annual warming. Ocean-

graphers attribute these early and rapid SST changes to dynamical processes associated with the slackening of the tradewinds (Philander, 1983). Many oceanographers, e.g. Wyrtki (1975), have attributed the initial east Pacific warming to a remote response initiated by one or more eastward propagating Kelvin waves, generated by wind changes in the central or western equatorial Pacific one-three months earlier. The more fundamental question of what causes the initial relaxation of the equatorial easterlies is still an issue of lively debate.

FIGURE 1. Composite SST anomalies derived by Rasmusson and Carpenter (1982) for six ENSO episodes between 1950 and 1976. Values are in $^{\circ}\text{C} \times 10$. Areas with positive anomalies greater than 0.4° are shaded. The evolution of the episode is illustrated by the sequence of three-month averaged values, which progresses from top to bottom of the figure.

By April(0) (Figure 1B) the SOI is usually falling rapidly, as positive and negative surface pressure anomalies increase at Darwin and Tahiti, respectively. SST anomalies near the Peru Coast have increased and spread westward along the equator merging with the positive anomalies around the dateline. Above normal rainfall is often observed in southwest Ecuador and northeast Peru associated with an eastern Pacific Intertropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ) slightly south of its normal position.

Of crucial importance to large-scale atmospheric forcing are the increasing positive rainfall anomalies near the dateline and corresponding negative anomalies over Southern Indonesia. These anomalies clearly signal the initial stages of a major eastward shift of the Maritime Continent convective region, including the South Pacific Convergence Zone (SPCZ) (Trenberth, 1976).

SST anomalies near the South American coast usually peak during April-June, a few months after the normal seasonal SST peak. Thus the typical warm episode results in an amplified and slightly retarded seasonal SST maximum. Rainfall anomalies in the eastern equatorial Pacific diminish as the ITCZ shifts northward with the season.

By mid-year(0) (Figure 1C), positive SST anomalies normally extend westward along the equator from the South American Coast across the dateline. Near the coast of the Americas, positive SST anomalies have typically spread poleward into the mid-latitudes of both hemispheres. This marks the time of a second more extensive collapse of the central equatorial Pacific easterlies (Rasmusson and Carpenter, 1982; Cane, 1983). Large positive precipitation anomalies cover a huge area of the central equatorial Pacific. Further west, regional droughts are common over portions of the monsoon region; South Indonesia, Australia and India, and later in the episode, southeast Africa. Prominent planetary-scale circulation anomalies also appear in the upper troposphere of the Southern Hemisphere (Arkin, 1982).

2.3 The Mature Stage

The typical warm episode reaches its mature stage near the end of year(0) (Figure 1D). The large SST, rainfall, and low-level circulation anomalies, which cover a huge area of the central equatorial Pacific, are near or past their peak. Low level westerly anomalies have disappeared from the western equatorial Pacific as rainfall over Australia and Indonesia tends toward normal values. At the same time, dry conditions develop over the North Pacific subtropics, from the southern Philippines westward across the Hawaiian Islands. This results in a change from a primarily east-west to a more north-south gradient in tropical Pacific rainfall anomalies.

The mature stage, which usually extends through the early months of year(+1), marks the truly global stage of the episode. Above normal temperatures exist throughout much of the tropical belt, both at the surface and throughout the troposphere (Pan and Oort, 1983; Chiu and Newell, 1983). Pronounced atmospheric circulation anomalies appear in the Northern Hemisphere with the seasonal progression into the boreal winter, while somewhat weakened anomalies persist in the Southern Hemisphere.

2.4 Decay Stage

The pattern of ENSO anomalies just described usually persists through the early months of year(+1), even as positive SST anomalies diminish over the equatorial Pacific. Below normal SST's typically reappear in the eastern Pacific during the warm season, and by mid-year (Figure 1E), near normal or even high index conditions are usually in evidence. Thus, the life cycle of a ENSO episode, from the beginning of the warming trend to the return of normal conditions, is usually 18-24 months.

3. The 1982/83 ENSO Episode

The typical ENSO episode described in Section 2 serves as a useful benchmark against which to compare the 1982/83 episode, which by most measures was among the strongest of the past century. For the most part, the expected global anomalies appeared and disappeared roughly on schedule, but the 1982/83 ENSO was also a striking reminder that no two episodes are alike in all major respects.

The general nature of this episode has been documented by Cane (1983), Rasmusson (1984), Rasmusson and Hall (1983), Rasmusson and Wallace (1983), Gill and Rasmusson (1983), as well as by articles in two issues of the Tropical Ocean-atmosphere Newsletter (1983a, 1983b). The following discussion is limited to a description of the SST and low-level atmospheric anomalies over the tropical Pacific.

3.1. Timing and Evolution of SST Anomalies

Major equatorial Pacific anomalies did not materialize until May-June 1982 (Figure 2). No significant buildup phase was observed during 1981, when the SOI and equatorial easterlies were near normal. While the surface pressure rise at Darwin in early 1982 was characteristic of the early stages of a typical ENSO episode, the pressure changes at Tahiti during late 1981-early 1982 were atypical, showing no appreciable fall until March 1982 (Figure 3).

Relatively small but widespread positive SST anomalies appeared over the central equatorial Pacific in May as drought conditions

FIGURE 2 - Longitude-time plots of mean monthly SST climatology and mean monthly values of SST, outgoing longwave radiation (OLR) and west wind component (U) anomalies during the 1982/83 ENSO episode. OLR and U plots are along the equator; SST plots are along the equator as far east as 95°W, then along the axis of maximum SST anomalies to the Peru Coast (8°S). The OLR anomalies are an index of rainfall anomalies, with negative values indicating above normal and positive values below normal rainfall.

developed over Australia. An unusually rapid fall in the SOI, associated with a collapse of the easterlies in the western equatorial Pacific began in June (Figure 3). The unusually rapid development during the period June-September resulted in an unusually strong pattern of ENSO anomalies. Contrary to the more typical events, this anomaly pattern did not evolve from an earlier warming near the South American coast (Figure 4). The strong warming at the coast did not materialize until October 1982.

FIGURE 3(A) - ENSO composite curves for nine events for Tahiti and Darwin surface pressure anomaly (H. van Loon, personal communication, 1983). (B) Similar curves for the 1982/83 ENSO episode from Rasmusson and Wallace (1983). Jul(0) is July 1982, etc. Note different ordinate (pressure anomaly) scales on the two diagrams.

A broad SST anomaly maximum was reached over the central and eastern Pacific near the end of the year, only a little later than usual. During the following months, SST anomalies west of 120°E showed a general decline (Figure 4), while to the east a second and larger maximum developed near the coast, spread westward to around 110°W , and peaked in June 1983.

Figure 4 illustrates these features. West of 120°W , the 1982/83 SST anomaly pattern was in the nature of a single event, and the timing was fairly typical. East of 110°W , the warming was more in the nature of two events,

FIGURE 4 - Time-longitude sections of mean monthly SST anomalies ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) for the 1982/83 ENSO episode (upper) and a three-event composite [Year(0) being 1957, 1965, and 1972]. Sections are along equator west of 95°W , and along the anomaly axis to the east as described for Figure 2. The contour intervals are 1°C for the upper and 0.5°C for the lower diagram (labeled in tenths), with greater than 2°C anomalies shaded.

and the timing was highly atypical. The usual early warming near the coast was entirely absent, but the characteristics and timing of the second peak are suggestive of such an event.

3.2 Eastward Progression

The striking development and evolution of the equatorial low-level wind and rainfall anomalies over a period of more than a year, and their association with the SST fields were perhaps the most striking aspects of this event. Figure 2 shows that positive rainfall anomalies (negative OLR anomalies) and low-level westerly wind anomalies appeared west of the dateline around May 1982, then migrated slowly eastward, crossing the entire equatorial Pacific during the subsequent 12-month period. The SST "warm-pool" showed a corresponding eastward migration which is seen by following the 28°C and 29°C isotherms (Figure 2). Note that SST's from 160°W to the dateline were already around 1°C above normal when the large rainfall and wind anomalies developed, indicating that an eastward broadening of the 29°C warm axis had already occurred. As the warm pool migrated eastward the zone of anomalous convection followed; thus it is the SST field rather than the SST anomaly field that is closely related to the anomalous convective activity. During all previous warm episodes since 1950, the 29°C isotherm had

never migrated east of 140°W; thus its eastward displacement to the coast of South America during the 1982/83 episode is another measure of its extreme intensity. By February 1983, the normal east-west SST gradient along the equator had been completely wiped out, with SST's above 28°C across the entire breadth of the equatorial Pacific (Figure 2).

4. Further Reflections on the 82/83 Episode

The reason for the atypical development of the 1982/83 SST anomaly pattern remains to be explained. It was pointed out in Section 3.1 that the timing of the 1982/83 central Pacific SST anomaly maximum was rather typical, while near the South American Coast the major warming also occurred at the normal time of year, but at the end, rather than the beginning of the episode. Although rare, this sequence of events may not be unprecedented, since the SST anomalies at Puerto Chicama, Peru show a broadly similar evolution during the 1940/41 episode.

Rasmusson and Wallace (1983) suggest that the typical ENSO episode can be viewed as being comprised of two sequential but interrelated events; (1) an initial warming near the eastern boundary which spreads westward, peaking by May-June and disappearing after mid-year. Onset of this event appears to be associated with a weakening of the southeast Pacific anticyclone which begins late in the previous year; (2) a broader scale warming of the equatorial Pacific from near the dateline eastward with its major development during mid-year, peaking near the end of the year, and disappearing a few months later. It is this second event which is of most importance to global atmospheric forcing because of the broad longitudinal extent of the warming and large area of associated anomalous convection. Viewed in this manner, atypical episodes consist of either an anomalous development of one of the two sequential events, or in the more unusual situation such as 1982/83, a reversal of the sequence.

This brief summary of the meteorological highlights of the 82/83 episode illustrates its importance for regional climate fluctuations on seasonal-interannual time scales. The 82/83 fluctuations have been relatively easy to document, because of their large amplitude and the fact that this warm episode has been by far the best measured and monitored to date.

Without question, the availability of new or improved satellite data products, or simply an increased amount of these data, coupled with lengthening observation time series of many routine satellite data products from which to evaluate departures from the norm, was the crucial new element in the system of atmospheric observations. Two important areas in which further improvement is vital, and seems clearly attainable, are the estimates of

low level winds from cloud motion data, and improved satellite estimates of SST. Unfortunately, satellite SST retrievals in the tropics were seriously degraded during much of the 82/83 episode because of aerosols injected into the atmosphere by the eruption of El Chichon in early April of 1982. Apart from this, the quality of operational NOAA SST retrievals has significantly improved since the introduction in late 1981 of the multi-channel technique, but further improvements are needed to resolve the small but important SST fluctuations in the western equatorial Pacific.

5. National & International Research Programs

The rapid expansion of our knowledge of the ENSO phenomenon during the past few years, together with the major climatic dislocations that accompanied the 1982/83 episode has resulted in a heightened awareness of the importance of this phenomenon to interannual climate variability. Largely in response to these developments, an international program, called Interannual Variability of the Tropical Ocean and the Global Atmosphere (TOGA) is now in the planning stage (Webster, 1984). The official objectives of TOGA are:

1. To understand the variations of the tropical ocean and global atmosphere on time scales of months to years, and to determine to what extent these variations are predictable.

2. To model the coupled ocean-atmosphere system for the purpose of predicting these variations.

3. To provide a scientific basis for designing a practical system for prediction (if models show that prediction seems feasible).

The oceanographic component of TOGA will be focused on the upper ocean in the tropics. If the dynamic factors that control the ocean's surface temperature in the tropics and the associated coupling between the ocean and the atmosphere can be understood, it is argued, then the evolution of the global response in the atmosphere might be modelled to provide a predictive capability. The TOGA ocean observational component will aim to describe conditions in the upper layer of the tropical oceans. Measurements include upper ocean temperatures, wind stress, air-sea heat fluxes, precipitation, sea level, and ocean currents. These measurements will be used to describe the space and time variations of the tropical upper ocean on a monthly time-scale and to evaluate the important physical processes involved. This information will be used to test and verify research models, both ocean and fully coupled ocean-atmosphere models, and ultimately may be used as routine input to forecasting models.

An atmospheric observational component will establish a limited amount of additional observations to supplement the existing World Weather Watch in order to produce a more comprehensive description of the global atmospheric circulation than is now possible. Special emphasis will be given to the tropical Pacific and monsoon regions and filling of gaps in the atmospheric coverage over the Southern Hemisphere.

Even before any analysis or interpretation of the data can be done, a system will be needed for collecting, transmitting, processing, and distributing the global data sets for TOGA. As TOGA evolves to the stage where satellites provide a significant amount of the ocean data, there will be a major challenge for the meteorologists and especially for the oceanographers just to keep up with the flow of data and information.

Part of the data handling problem may be traced to the differing customs of the two scientific communities involved in TOGA. Meteorologists are accustomed to working with global data sets, and, particularly during the Global Atmospheric Research Program (GARP), such sets were routinely managed and distributed. Meteorologists also share the operational data from the World Weather Watch system, which is collected and available within a few hours of observation time, as basic data for research. Oceanographers, on the other hand, do not have such a tradition. Even the largest scale oceanographic experiments to date have had regional limits. Furthermore, oceanographers are used to collecting their own data, and working on them alone for a year or two before sharing them. However, experience during the 1982/83 ENSO episode gives reason for optimism that a system of rapid data dissemination will also be developed for oceanographic data.

When the 1982/83 episode began, the available operational oceanographic data consisted of the ship of opportunity data transmitted over the global telecommunication system (GTS) of the World Weather Watch. There were, however, other observations being taken in the tropical Pacific, notably as part of the NOAA Equatorial Pacific Ocean Climate Studies (EPOCS) program, the NSF PEQUOD program, as well as the observational programs of the west coast South American nations. In addition, Prof. Klaus Wyrtki (U. of Hawaii) was obtaining data from his network of sea level gauges. These, however, were largely "research" rather than real time monitoring programs. As the episode evolved, however, a remarkable transformation took place. Reports of observations taken on EPOCS and PEQUOD cruises were summarized and widely disseminated within days of acquisition. Efforts were made to speed up the transmission of data from the EPOCS fixed buoy, and Dr. Donald Hansen of the NOAA Atlantic Oceanographic and

Meteorological Laboratories took action to enter the data from his drifting buoys on the GTS system. In addition, international cooperation, which had been developing over a period of years, between U.S. and South American scientists payed off in the form of near real time exchange of information from land stations and research vessels. Special "rapid response" research aircraft flights and an augmented ship of opportunity program were implemented by EPOCS in an effort to plug a few of the monitoring gaps. All in all, this resulted in a near blurring of the conventional line between oceanographic research and monitoring observations, and the most rapid exchange among countries, institutions and individuals of near real time oceanographic and fishing information that has ever transpired in response to a climate disturbance in the Western Hemisphere.

The organization of TOGA is carried out under the auspices of a number of international agencies. The international arrangements are complicated. For research planning, the oceanographers have an organization called the Committee on Climatic Changes and the Ocean (CCCO). The meteorologists have the Joint Scientific Committee (JSC) of the World Climate Research Program (WCRP). Jointly, CCCO and JSC sponsor the Scientific Steering Group for TOGA. The TOGA Steering Group meets every few months to formulate the scientific priorities and to provide scientific guidance on the implementation of the TOGA program.

To communicate with government and scientists worldwide, a TOGA Conference will be held at UNESCO Headquarters in Paris in September 1984. TOGA is scheduled to begin officially on 1 January 1985. The Conference, it is hoped, will serve to inform national representatives and scientists of the program and to stimulate participation.

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